

ACMEOLOGY APPROACH IN PROVIDING PROFESSIONAL IMPROVEMENT OF FUTURE TEACHERS

Bakriddinov Dostonbek Bakhtiyor oglu

Doctoral Candidate, Namangan state pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18647901>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 11th February 2026

Accepted: 12th February 2026

Online: 13th February 2026

KEYWORDS

acmeological approach, professional development, future teacher, pedagogical skills, creative activity, higher pedagogical education, professional development, acmeological culture

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the theoretical and methodological foundations of the acmeological approach in ensuring the professional development of future teachers. The issues of ensuring the professional skills, creative activity and personal development of future teachers through the introduction of the acmeological approach in the process of higher pedagogical education are analyzed. The study substantiates diagnostic criteria, methods and technologies that serve to form the acmeological orientation of future primary school teachers and develop their professional and spiritual and psychological potential. Also, the need to modernize the content of pedagogical education within the framework of the acmeological approach is scientifically substantiated.

In today's conditions of globalization and scientific and technological progress, the demands placed on the education system are increasing. The sharp increase in the flow of information, the rapid renewal of educational content require constant improvement of the professional skills and creative potential of pedagogical personnel. In particular, the professional training of future educators involved in educating the younger generation is one of the important factors of social development.

From this point of view, there is a need to rely on modern methodological approaches in the process of training pedagogical personnel in the system of higher pedagogical education.[1] One of such approaches is the acmeological approach, which is aimed at studying the processes of achieving a high peak in a person's professional activity and fully realizing their potential. The acmeological approach is of great theoretical and practical importance in developing the professional maturity, spiritual maturity and creative activity of future educators.

As one of the important conditions for the implementation of these tasks, there is a need for systematic development of professional qualifications and pedagogical skills of the country's workers, especially pedagogical personnel engaged in the education of the younger generation.[2] Because in the current era, as a result of a sharp increase in the volume of information and the acceleration of scientific and technological progress, some aspects of existing pedagogical, psychological, methodological and practical training are becoming obsolete to a certain extent. This situation requires special attention to the development of professional skills and creative potential of specialists engaged in pedagogical activities. One

of the important factors in meeting these needs and requirements is the introduction of modern technologies aimed at developing professional skills into the educational process. From this point of view, improving the pedagogical skills and professional and pedagogical training of specialists working in educational areas, in particular in the field of physical culture and sports, is of great importance.

The main goal of implementing the acmeological approach is to take into account the acmeological orientation of the individual, the conditions of the organizational environment, and the specific characteristics of the subjects of higher education institutions where this approach is implemented. In the process of research, the conditions that determine the possibilities and success of implementing the acmeological approach were analyzed.[3] One of the urgent tasks facing modern higher education is to develop a model for developing the professional skills of future primary school teachers based on the acmeological approach, and this process is inextricably linked with the development of moral self-awareness by strengthening their spiritual and professional-psychological potential. The study highlighted the fact that factors such as health, a positive attitude to life, and trust in society and people serve to develop spirituality in students as a valuable component of acmeological culture. Also, a methodology for determining and assessing the level of formation of the acmeological orientation of future primary school teachers was developed in detail, and the conditions for gradually ensuring the acmeological development of students' personal characteristics were determined.

It was substantiated that the process of diagnosing the professional development of future primary school teachers based on the acmeological approach and assessing its effectiveness can be carried out through methods such as oral survey, analysis of the educational process and results, self-education, reflexive goal setting, pedagogical observation of practical professional activities, self- and expert assessment.[4]

Based on the goals and objectives set at the main stage, stages of improving the methodology for developing the professional skills of future primary school teachers based on the acmeological approach were determined. Acmeological technologies with high development potential include business, reflexive, organizational-activity and communicative games, professional training, situational and acmeological exercises, and modeling of professional situations.

At the initial stage, the level of the acmeological position of the future primary school teacher was diagnosed before and after the introduction of technologies, and the dynamics of the development of the acmeological position during professional training were determined.[5] At the second stage, methods aimed at forming an acmeological position were used, and training sessions were organized aimed at understanding the real and potential content and values of pedagogical activity.

At the same time, the reflective skills of future primary school teachers were developed through reflexive training. Within the framework of these trainings, the skills of understanding the motives of pedagogical activity, understanding professional success, imagining oneself as a professional person, analyzing metaphors related to the roles of a teacher and a student, and solving complex pedagogical situations were formed.

In general, the acmeological approach serves as an important methodological basis for training future teachers in the process of higher pedagogical education and improving the professional activities of current teachers. This approach requires the organization of the content of higher education on the basis of humanization, systematic, activity-oriented, person-oriented, philosophical-anthropological and synergetic approaches. Therefore, it is urgent to introduce the acmeological approach as a priority in the process of modernization of the content of pedagogical education.[6]

In conclusion, the acmeological approach is of significant pedagogical importance in ensuring the professional development of future teachers. This approach allows organizing the content of higher pedagogical education on the basis of humanization, person-oriented and activity-oriented approaches. Based on the acmeological approach, the development of professional skills, creative thinking, reflexive abilities and acmeological culture of future teachers is achieved.

Also, the use of acmeological technologies, trainings and diagnostic methods serves to improve the professional training of future teachers. As a result, the effectiveness of pedagogical activity increases and the necessary conditions are created for the implementation of innovative approaches in the educational process. Therefore, the widespread introduction of the acmeological approach in the system of higher pedagogical education is one of the urgent tasks of modern education.

References:

1. Zimnyaya, I. A. Pedagogical Psychology. Moscow, 2010.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi. 2019.
3. Zimnyaya I.A. Psychology and Personality Development. Moscow: Academy, 2019.
4. Vigotsky L.S. Educational Psychology. Moscow, 2016.
5. Derkach A. Acmeology: Human Development at the Peak of Professionalism. Moscow, 2004.
6. Anan'ev, B. G. Man as a Subject of Knowledge. St. Petersburg, 2001.